

PSYCHOTHERAPY

ATTACHMENT THEORY

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a comprehensive analysis of John Bowlby's attachment theory, highlighting its foundational principles, key components, and impact on human development across the lifespan. Attachment theory posits that individuals are biologically predisposed to form emotional bonds with primary caregivers, which serve as a secure base for exploration, emotional regulation, and social development. The paper explores the formation of attachment bonds, the critical role of caregivers, and sensitive periods during early childhood that shape attachment patterns. Bowlby's typology of attachment styles including secure, avoidant, anxious-ambivalent, and disorganized are examined in relation to emotional, psychological, and social outcomes. The concept of internal working models is discussed as a mechanism through which early experiences influence perceptions of self and others. Cultural considerations, clinical applications, and limitations of Bowlby's theory are also evaluated. Despite criticisms, attachment theory remains a cornerstone of developmental psychology, providing valuable insights for research and clinical practice in understanding the enduring influence of early relational experiences on emotional well-being and interpersonal functioning.

1. 1. OVERVIEW

Attachment theory, first developed by John Bowlby during the 20th century, states that people are biologically predisposed to create emotional bonds with those around them and to ensure survival. This usually takes place during the early developmental period of child, through interaction with their caregivers which include mothers, parents, siblings) and their environment, (Scharfe, 2017). This evolutionary approach supports survival through the promotion of proximity seeking behaviours in children. This allows them to stay close to their primary caregiver for their protection and welfare as well as nurturing and general security. An attachment is a deep emotional bond between and individual and other people, (Thompson, Simpson & Berlin, 2022, Scharfe, 2017). Attachment styles for human beings are important aspects of how they will relate to themselves, those around them and the world at large. The ideologies of Bowlby are deeply rooted in the psychoanalytic school of thought which has significant interest in the understanding of early life experiences and their impact in shaping, personality, (Harlow., 2021). Social competence, emotional development across the lifespan of human beings. This paper will provide an analysis of the attachment theory and explore the history, context, key principles and their impact on developmental psychology.

2. ATTACHMENT THEORY

The concept of attachment ideologies is found in the work of John Bowlby, (Bowlby, 1944, Bowlby, 1969, Bowlby, 1973, Bowlby, 1980). John Bowlby (1907-1990) was a British psychiatrist and psychoanalyst, usually considered the pioneer of attachment theory. Having been trained as a Freudian psychoanalyst, Bowlby's work was significantly influenced by the ideologies of Sigmund Freud psychoanalytic approach as well as ethology, evolutionary biology cybernetics and developmental psychology, (Thompson, et al, 2022, Scharfe, 2017). Bowlby developed his groundbreaking theoretical tenants through observation of children who were experiencing material deprivation, and separation during the World War II thereby revolutionising developmental psychology. Bowlby's work focused mostly on the emotional relationships developed between infants and caregivers, which he believed were biologically grounded and necessary for human survival, (Cassidy, Jones, & Shaver, 2013).

3. FOUNDATIONAL PRINCIPLES

The attachment ideologies are rooted in the belief that *attachment behaviours are innate and adaptive*, that is; they are instinctual and adaptable in functioning in order to

maintain closeness or proximity to their primary carer, who is identified as a secure base from where the infant or child draws security, protection, nurturing and their lens and aid for discovering and experiencing their environment, (Cassidy et al, 2013, Scharfe, 2016). Bowlby's ideologies further posit that children separated from their caregivers demonstrate distress as well as withdrawal and various maladaptive tendencies or behaviours, (Scharfe, 2017). This shows significant importance of early childhood development and the quality of early life attachment and their influence in the child's development, social and psychological growth.

4. KEY COMPONENTS OF BOWLBY'S THEORY

Bowlby significantly re-shapes and redefines understanding of emotional and psychological development of children and adults. This paper will outline three key components of the attachment theory, which are *the attachment bond*, *the importance of the primary caregiver*, and the *critical and sensitive periods* which are defined as being central to the formation of attachment styles.

4.1 The Concept of the Attachment Bond

The concept of attachment bonds is a significant and central principle of Bowlby's attachment theory. It is important in the formation of emotional bonds between individuals specifically children and their caregivers such as the mother or the father. Key elements of the attachment bond is the *proximity and security*.

4.1.1 Proximity and security

Proximity is defined as the emotional closeness that individuals pursue with their attachment figures, which can be parents or romantic partners or friends, (Garrett, 2023). Emotional closeness is critical in the maintenance of the attachment bond and facilitates security and support. When an individual is feeling lost, distressed or experiencing life challenges and threats they pursue their attachment figures for comfort and reassurance, (Garret, 2023, Thomas et al, 2022). An example is a baby in a room full of other people. The baby may start to feel anxious and instinctively seek their primary caregiver, which is their mother who in turn responds with open arms, a smile or comforting words with reassures the baby that they are safe to explore the room despite the presence of other people. Bowlby referred to this interaction as *proximity maintenance*. It is importance in the formation of relationship patterns throughout a lifespan.

Attachment bonds are foundational and experienced and formed during early life but extend into adulthood, therefore impacting social connections and romantic

partnerships (Garrett, 2023). An adult who is facing challenges at work may reach out to their partner for support, who in turn listens and reassures them with words of comfort. This helps the individual to feel safe, understood, supported and develop the ability to express their feelings and find ways to cope. Understanding attachment bonds is crucial in the management of psychological and social issues such as development psychopathology and the impact of separation and loss. The concept of the impact attachment bonds is qualified by the type of relationship an individual has with their attachment figure (healthy or unhealthy).

4.2 The Importance of the Primary Caregiver

Bowlby describes the caregiver as the significant role in the development of an individual's attachment bond as well their psychological wellbeing of child. The caregiver is the foundation of the attachment relationship (*the attachment figure*), which shapes safety, trust, understanding, emotional security and support. An attachment figure who is responsive and sensitive influences the development of secure attachments which are deemed significant in the development of a healthy emotional and psychological state, (Bowlby, 1969, Garrett, 2023). The caregiver is critical for their *influence on developmental* outcomes of the person or child. These include social, relationship formation, work relationships, social skills, emotional regulation, communication skills, responses to other people and general association in social, work, school and family spaces, (Yip et al., 2017, Ackerman, 2019).

Secure attachments provide positive outcomes, and insecure ones cause emotional distress and difficulties in relationships, (Casidy et al, 2013). Caregivers provide a *secure base* for their partner or child to explore the world. When people generally feel safe and protected and supported, they actively engage in exploration and learning. This primary aspect is necessary for psychological and physical development. Attachment patterns with attachment figures serve as the *templates for future relationship* formation as children transform from children to adults, healthy attachments produce healthy relationship skills and unhealthy ones produce challenges, (Thomas et al, 2022). Primary caregivers also provide intervention and support which in turn produce healthy attachment bonds and are key in the development of the holistic wellbeing of the individual through out their lifespan from childhood to adulthood, (Bowlby, 1944, Bowlby, 1969, Bowlby, 1973, Bowlby, 1980).

4.3 Critical and Sensitive Periods

Critical sensitive period is crucial in the development of attachment bonds. These periods refer to specific times of development during an individual's life span. For example, a period involving, specific experiences and stimuli occurrence which influence development. The critical period according to Bowlby, (1944, 1969) is childhood.

If an individual does not develop secure attachment bonds during the critical and sensitive period of childhood, then they are at risk of developing long term emotional struggles and relationship difficulties, (Scharfe, 2017).

Sensitive periods are times within an individual's life when they experience receptiveness to specific experiences. Sensitive periods can be seen during the developmental milestones of a child. Bowlby's theory suggests that critical periods of attachment formation are between the ages of 2–3 years of life, (Scharfe, 2017). This is the critical sensitive window for attachment development which produces long life irreversible consequences. An example of a sensitive period occurs during the oral stage, of Freud's psychosexual development stages, from birth to about 18 months period. During this stage, babies experience oral interaction and comfort from sucking milk (feeding), biting, and chewing which are key for establishing trust and security. The baby at this stage requires nourishment and comfort through feeding and oral stimulation (stimuli). Positive oral experiences can foster a sense of safety, but unpleasant encounters might lead to later-life reliance and trust issues, (Thomas et al, 2023)

5. BOWLBY'S ATTACHMENT STYLES

Bowlby's attachment theory identifies attachment styles that develop with the early childhood phase of interactions between a child and their primary caregiver. These attachment styles of *secure attachment*, *insecure-avoidant*, *insecure-ambivalent (resistant)*, and *disorganized attachment*, show the different kinds of patterns of emotional connection and responses to separation by individuals. This paper will outline the different types of attachment styles according to Bowlby, (Thomas et al, 2023, Bowlby, 1944, Bowlby, 1969).

5.1 Secure Attachment

Secure attachment is an important aspect of attachment theory since it shows a child's healthy and positive emotional connection with their primary caregiver. This occurs when a carer is consistently responsive and sensitive to the needs of the infant, therefore providing a secure or reliable source for security, comfort and care, (Scharfe, 2017). Secure attachments help to develop trust, security and safety and the ability to grow and explore their environment with confidence, (Vrticka et al., 2012, Yip et al., 2017). Secure attachment characteristics for development are *proximity-seeking*, which involves closeness to the attachment figure in times of distress for comfort and safety and reassurance. *Exploration* which involves, the ability to explore their environment and engage in play activities with others while they are reassured of safety. This is essential for physical and cognitive development in early life, (Thomas et al, 2023). *Emotional regulation* which involves the development of emotional regulation abilities

which allow them to regulate and manage their emotional and coping strategies in times of distress through consistent support for their attachment figures, (Robledo et al., 2022). Secure attachments produce many positive outcomes, such as healthy relationships, emotional wellbeing and social competence.

5.2 Insecure Attachment

Insecure attachments are characterised by a lack of consistent support and responsiveness from the attachment figures which result in various psychological problems which manifest in various forms, (Robledo et al., 2022).

5.3 Avoidant attachment

Infants or children with avoidant attachment issues usually distance themselves from their attachment figures (carer). They appear to be emotionally detached as well as indifferent. These infants avoid closeness and show little distress when separated from their carer due to their unresponsiveness, (Scharfe, 2017).

5.3.1 *Anxious (Ambivalent) Attachment*

Infants or people with anxious attachment present clinginess and heightened anxiety about separation from their attachment figures. They usually become extremely distressed when their caregiver or attachment figure has to leave them for a certain period of time and in turn show ambivalent behaviours upon the return of their attachment figures, (reunion), for example, resisting comfort, (Thomas et al, 2023). Individuals develop this type of attachment due to an inconsistent caregiving pattern for example where, attachment figures are sometimes responsive and other period neglectful or even abusive.

5.3.2 *Disorganized Attachment*

Disorganised attachment is characterized by an absence of a clear attachment figure strategy. Individuals experiencing disorganized attachment may display contradictory behaviours, such as approaching the attachment figure and upon response, present with fear, (Robledo et al., 2022). This is seen in individuals who have attachment figures who are traumatising frightening in nature of caring and support and times kind and nice. This causes confusion to the individual, (Scharfe, 2017).

Insecure attachment causes significant implication on the emotional and physical development of the infant or individual. They struggle with managing their emotions, which results in increased anxiety, depression and behavioural issues at school or society at large. These unhealthy attachments influence relationship difficulties, which lead to difficulties in the formation of relationships in adulthood and difficulties with

trust and intimacy as well as emotional closeness to other people, (Scharfe, 2017). Attachment issues present with social competence problems where individuals experience difficulties in reading social cues and interacting with other people.

6. ANALYSIS OF THE ATTACHMENT STYLES

6.1 Impact on Development

Insecure attachment can have long term impacts on a infants' emotional, psychological and social development. Children who have insecure attachments frequently struggle with emotional dysregulation, which can appear as increased anxiety in some cases, depression, and behavioral problems, (Thomas et, al, 2023). These children present difficulties in coping with stress, behavioural issues and various maladaptive behaviours, including acts of violence towards others and withdrawal. The absence of a *safe basis* from which to explore their surroundings and develop stable and balanced emotional foundation can cause significant impairment in social competencies therefore, making it difficult for them to build healthy interactions with those around them, (Vrticka et al., 2012, Yip et al., 2017, Ackerman, 2019)

(Robledo et al., 2022). Individuals with insecure attachment present with continued struggles in their interpersonal connections as they mature into teenagers and adults, therefore, frequently repeating patterns of mistrust and emotional distancing with others. This can lead to a cycle of insecurity in which the individual struggles to make meaningful connections, exacerbating feelings of isolation and mental misery, (Scharfe, 2017).

A study was conducted by Hepper and Carnelley (2010), to understand how attachment style affects personal engagement as a result of feedback seeking behavior from friends or those close to them. The study found that attachment styles and attachments figures influenced feedback seeking behaviours which affect self-perception, both positively and negatively.

6.2 Bowlby's Internal Working Models

Bowlby's hypothesis of internal working models is significant in understanding how early attachment experiences affect individual expectations and interactions in relationships throughout their lifespan. These internal working models are mental representations established by a child's interactions with their primary caregiver, which influence how they perceive themselves and others, (Harlow., 2021). An example is an individual who experiences a consistent caring and responsive attachment figure. This person is most likely to develop positive internal working model and with a positive self-perception and perception of others, while those with insecure

attachment develop negative internal working model with a negative self-perception and that of others, (unworthy or others as untrustworthy), (Casidy et al, 2013). These models shape emotional responses, relational dynamics, and coping methods, ultimately influencing an individual's social and emotional functioning in a variety of circumstances.

A study by Vrticka, et al, (2012) examined individual perceptions of relationships through an assessment of attachment type in relation to emotional reactions in social and non-social circumstances using the Adult Attachment Questionnaire (AQQ) and MRI. They investigated whether attachment orientations are associated with increases or declines in social and emotional processing in the brain. Based on brain responses, the researchers discovered that participants with high aversion responded to positive social signals by experiencing lower activation of affective processes, and that individuals with high anxious attachment processed socially aversive situations through brain system association with fear. These results show the biological bases of attachment styles in individuals as stated by Bowlby's internal working model and his hypothesis for innate instincts, (Scharfe, 2017).

6.3 Cultural Consideration and Application in Therapy

Cultural issues are critical for a thorough knowledge of attachment types and their therapeutic implications. Attachment behaviours and perceptions of caregiver attentiveness can vary greatly between cultures. Certain cultures, for example, individualistic cultures may prioritize independence and self-sufficiency, whilst others collective cultures promote interdependence and communal caregiving. This cultural diversity highlights the importance of a culturally sensitive approach in therapeutic settings, where therapists must recognize and respect their clients' individual backgrounds and values. Recognizing a client's attachment style within their cultural framework might help to influence treatment techniques and interventions. Therapists can help caregivers become more sensitive and responsive by treating individual attachment difficulties while also considering the larger cultural forces that shape these experiences. The integrating of cultural awareness into therapeutic practices, help clinicians to be more supportive of their clients in the development of healthier attachment patterns and enhancing their emotional wellbeing.

7. CRITICISMS AND LIMITATIONS OF BOWLBY'S THEORY

Bowlby's attachment theory has helped us understand the dynamics of child-caregiver relationships and how they affect development. However, it has received various criticisms and restrictions that should be considered. Firstly, there is an *overemphasis on the mother-child or parent-caregiver relationship* which forms the primary critics of this theory. Critics contend that this viewpoint overlooks the importance of fathers,

siblings, and other caretakers in a child's development. Research has demonstrated that children can create stable attachments with numerous caregivers, and the quality of these ties has a substantial impact on their emotional and social development, (Casidy et al, 2013, Scharfe, 2017). The theory is also criticised for *cultural biases* as it was developed in the western context and industrialised societies where Bowlby observed children and their behaviours in accordance with attachment styles and overlook cultural aspects of collectivists. Bowlby's theory has been criticized for *assuming a deterministic view of attachment*, indicating that early encounters with caregivers rigidly shape future relationships and emotional functioning. Critics argue that this attitude underestimates people's capacity for change and resilience, (Thomas et al 2023, Scharfe, 2017). Many people can build secure attachments later in adulthood, even if they had insecure attachments as children, demonstrating that attachment types are not fixed and can change with new experiences and connections, (Harlow., 2021). Bowlby's theory has a primary focus in early life experiences without applying much attention to adulthood or later development. Events such as trauma, loss, and the influence of supportive attachment figures in adult relationships can impact the development of healthy adult attachment styles. People can change and their experiences can shape new insights as individuals are constantly evolving

8. CONCLUSION

In this work, the author examines the fundamental components of Bowlby's attachment theory, such as the main components of the attachment bond, the relevance of the primary caregiver, and the critical periods for attachment development. The paper examined the various attachment styles identified by Bowlby and their impact on psychological and emotional as well as social development, and reviewed criticisms of the theory. Attachment theory is still one of the most influential frameworks in developmental psychology, providing important insights into how early relationship experiences impact long-term emotional and social outcomes. Despite its shortcomings, it continues to contribute to research and clinical practice, particularly in understanding the causes of emotional illnesses and the therapeutic mending of relational bonds. A recommendation is that future attachment research should focus on improving the concept of internal working models, investigating the neurological basis of attachment, and addressing the cross-cultural applicability of Bowlby's original paradigm. Nonetheless, the core premise of Bowlby's theory that early caregiving interactions are essential for emotional development is as important today as it was when it was initially proposed.

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